

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

THE RELEVANCE OF GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCHES OF PORTALS¹

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Abstract

The article proves that the version of the special theory of relativity (STR) presented in physics textbooks is incorrect. This is because in the early 20th century science lacked experimental knowledge required for the STR to be created, and the postulate (called the principle of light speed non-exceedance) that replaced the knowledge turned out to be incorrect and has been experimentally refuted in the 21st century. It is explained that tsunami and piano music would not exist, church bells would not ring and even swings would not swing on playgrounds, if the generally accepted version of the STR were true. Moreover, this version of the STR also implies that Ohm's law as interpreted by Steinmetz used daily by millions of radio and electrical engineers in their practice does not exist, and therefore radio engineering and electrical engineering should not exist either.

That is why, an alternative version of the STR has been created instead of the incorrect one. It follows from this that there is an invisible Multiverse whose universes are interconnected by numerous portals, including those located on Earth. And at least some of anomalous zones are entrances to portals. Geophysical exploration of portals are very necessary, as they will allow us to obtain new valuable knowledge about our Multiverse and confirm the correctness of the alternative version of STR.

Keywords: portals, parallel universes, Multiverse, special theory of relativity, physical reality of imaginary numbers, dark matter, dark energy

1. Introduction

Portals, sometimes also called 'star gates' [1], understood as transitions from some universes to others, are the subject of research in the article. Therefore, it is clear that one can speak of portals only if there are at least two universes, i.e. Multiverses. The term 'Multiverse' meaning two and more universes was proposed by the American philosopher-psychologist William James in 1895 and introduced to practice by the English science fiction writer Michael John Moorcock. To date, a large number of Multiverse hypotheses have been proposed. The most informative of them are [2]-[13].

But the special theory of relativity (STR) [14]-[16] recognized in physics as the greatest scientific achievement of the 20th century, denies existence of Multiverses at all and claims that there is only our visible universe.

Yet, there are a very large number of the so-called anomalous zones [17]-[20] planet. They are fraught with phenomena incapable of being explained by modern science. At least some of them are supposedly entrances to portals. Geophysical exploration of portals will allow visiting them safely and solving some important problems of modern astrophysics successfully.

2. The version of the special theory of relativity presented for study in physics textbooks is incorrect

The alternative version of the STR states the generally recognized version of the STR studied in physics textbooks to be incorrect [21]-[32], because:

- the relativistic formulas obtained therein are incorrect;
- the relativistic formulas have been incorrectly explained using the incorrect principle of light speed non-exceedance;
- the relativistic formulas have entailed wrong conclusions consisting in physical unreality of imaginary numbers and existence of only our visible universe.

Hence the alternative version of the STR thereby asserts exactly what we need – the existence of other universes, besides our universe, which together form the Multiverse. This follows from its relativistic formulas that are different from those in the generally accepted version of the STR. In order to understand the relativistic formulas of the alternative version of the STR better, let us first consider the simpler relativistic formulas of the generally accepted version of the STR. They are as follow

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta t = \Delta t_0 \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$l = l_0 \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \quad (3)$$

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Fig. 1. Graphs of functions $m(v)$, $\Delta t(v)$ and $l(v)$ corresponding to the existing and alternative versions of the STR in the subluminal $v < C$ and superluminal $v > C$ ranges

where m is the relativistic mass of a moving body;

m_0 is the rest mass of a moving body;

Δt is the relativistic time of a moving body;

Δt_0 is the rest time of a moving body;

l is the relativistic length of a moving body;

l_0 is the rest length of a moving body;

v is the velocity of a moving body;

C is the speed of light.

Fig. 1a,b,c presents the graphs of the formulas. As can be seen, all formulas for $v < C$ lead to results measured by real numbers, and for $v > C$ to results measured by imaginary numbers. This circumstance greatly discouraged authors of the generally accepted version of the STR, since until very recently no one could explain physical sense of the results measured by imaginary numbers discovered 500 years ago. And no one would need a theory whose results could not be explained even by its creators. The fate of the generally accepted (but it's only now, not then) version of the STR hung in the balance in the early 20th century. It was saved by introducing a postulate, i.e. an unproven assumption, called the principle of light speed non-exceedance, the sense of which is clear from its name. The postulate looked quite acceptable, since in the early 20th century physics knew no phenomenon, in which any physical entity would move with superluminal velocity. This is how the STR has begun to be studied and still been studied even in the most prestigious universities

But in 1934, Cherenkov radiation was discovered [33]. The radiation is emitted when electrically charged particles are moving at speeds faster than that of light. In 1958, Pavel Alekseevich Cherenkov, Igor Evgenievich Tamm and Ilya Mikhailovich Frank received

the Nobel Prize for the discovery and explanation of this radiation. The fate of the STR hung in the balance again. And the STR was saved once again. This time it was saved by making a clarification that the principle of light speed non-exceedance had implied the speed of light exclusively in a vacuum.

In the 21st century, one more attempt to refute the STR was undertaken. This time it was the OPERA experiment at the Large Hadron Collider. It was supposed to register superluminal neutrinos and thereby prove physical reality of imaginary numbers. A sensational report about successful completion of the very complex and expensive experiment was published on September 22, 2011. However, six months later, the OPERA experiment was refuted by the ICARUS experiment. Therefore, the STR again failed to be refuted.

Nevertheless, in 2008-2010, i.e. before publication of the OPERA experiment results, the results of alternative studies of special processes in linear electric circuits [34]-[38], were published. They proved that resonance, discovered by Galileo in 1602, occurs at complex frequencies, rather than at real ones, which has still been stated in textbooks on the theory of linear electric circuits. Thus, physical reality of imaginary numbers has been finally proved and the unsuccessful OPERA experiment has become useless. And since

mathematics is the language of all exact sciences, the principle of physical reality of imaginary numbers proven experimentally in the theory of linear electric circuits has become generally scientific. Therefore, this time the principle of light speed non-exceedance has been refuted.

At the same time, it has been also proved that if the outdated version of the STR presented in physics textbooks were true, then tsunami, bell ringing and music of piano or other musical instruments would be impossible; swings would not swing in a playground; Ohm's law as interpreted by Steinmetz used daily by millions of radio engineers all over the world would not work; and there would be no radio and electrical engineering at all. However, authors of the incorrect version of the STR did not know this when they created their theory at the beginning of the 20th century, but later physicists-relativists did not want to know this. Moreover, they did everything so that no one knew about it. For example, they staged a misleading and very expensive advertising action in the form of OPERA and ICARUS experiments at the Large Hadron Collider.

Nevertheless, physical reality of imaginary numbers has already been proven and the truth of this statement is beyond doubt. And therefore, in accordance with the relativistic formulas (1)-(3), something must exist in nature at . However, analysis of the formulas has shown that the universes corresponding to such a situation should be physically unstable and therefore self-liquidating, i.e. could not exist. Thus, the relativistic formulas (1)-(3) are incorrect as well as the generally accepted version of the STR.

The generally accepted version of the STR turned out to be incorrect because, due to the lack of necessary scientific knowledge in the early 20th century, relativistic formulas were derived incorrectly. Postulates were

used instead of missing scientific knowledge. However, the principle of light speed non-exceedance turned out to be wrong. Derivation errors were not timely detected and corrected. In subsequent years, following the inertia of competitive struggle (after all, within the framework of a market economy, science is a kind of business), the STR turned out to be so canonized that it became poorly receptive to new knowledge. As a result, the relativistic formulas have not yet been corrected.

3. Alternative version of the special theory of relativity

3.1. There is a hidden Multiverse in nature, not a Monoverse

Actually, relativistic formulas obtained in the generally accepted version of the STR not only were not, but could not be explained, because functions (1)-(3) vary in significantly different ways (see Fig. 1 a,b,c) in the subluminal (for $v < c$) and superluminal (for $v > c$) velocity ranges. As has been shown above, universes corresponding to the formulas (1)–(3) are physically unstable in the superluminal velocity range (for $v > c$) and, therefore, cannot even exist. That is why the formulas (1)-(3) are incorrect. In order for the same regularities to take place in the subluminal (for $v < c$) and superluminal (for $v > c$) velocity ranges and, therefore, formulas describing the corresponding processes could be explained, the graphs $m(v)$, $\Delta t(v)$, $l(v)$ should take the form shown in Fig.

1d,e,f. This requires introduction of the function i^q into the corrected relativistic formulas of the STR corresponding to them

$$m(q) = \frac{m_0 i^q}{\sqrt{1 - (v/c - q)^2}} = \frac{m_0 i^q}{\sqrt{1 - (w/c)^2}} \tag{4}$$

$$\Delta t(q) = \Delta t_0 i^q \sqrt{1 - (v/c - q)^2} = \Delta t_0 i^q \sqrt{1 - (w/c)^2} \tag{5}$$

$$l(q) = l_0 i^q \sqrt{1 - (v/c - q)^2} = l_0 i^q \sqrt{1 - (w/c)^2} \tag{6}$$

where $q(v) = \lfloor v/c \rfloor$ – is the 'floor' function of discrete mathematics (Figure 2a);

$w = v - qc$ is its own local velocity for each universe (Fig. 2b).

And the function i^q is the simple and clear function convenient for this situation, since, for integers of the argument q , it takes on only the proper values $+1, +i, -1, -i$ and in the proper sequence.

These values correspond to four different universes alternating in space. However, its values are unknown for non-integers of the argument. This is not actually a problem, since we can replace the function i^q in the formulas (4)-(6) by the Euler's formula $e^{iq\pi/2} = \cos(q\pi/2) + i \sin(q\pi/2)$ that takes on the same values $+1, +i, -1, -i$ for integers of the argument q and, therefore, can completely replace it

Fig. 2. Graphs of functions $q(v)$ and $w(v)$ illustrating the meaning of the 'floor' function of discrete mathematics

$$m(q) = \frac{m_0 e^{iq\pi/2}}{\sqrt{1-(v/c-q)^2}} = \frac{m_0 [\cos(q\pi/2) + i \sin(q\pi/2)]}{\sqrt{1-(w/c)^2}} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta t(q) = \Delta t_0 e^{iq\pi/2} \sqrt{1-(v/c-q)^2} = \Delta t_0 [\cos(q\pi/2) + i \sin(q\pi/2)] \sqrt{1-(w/c)^2} \quad (8)$$

$$l(q) = l_0 e^{iq\pi/2} \sqrt{1-(v/c-q)^2} = l_0 [\cos(q\pi/2) + \sin(q\pi/2)] \sqrt{1-(w/c)^2} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 3. Estimated helical structure of the hidden Multiverse

Thus the corrected relativistic formulas (4)-(6) and (7)-(9) imply that the quantity q takes on integers² (see

² It takes non-integer values in the portals considered below, in which, from their entrance to exit, under the influence of

physical factors that have not yet been studied, the value changes by on

Fig. 2a), determined by the discrete ‘floor’ function $q(v) = \lfloor v/c \rfloor$. The integers correspond to different universes. Thus, the quantity $q = 0$ corresponds to our visible universe (for which $i^0 = 1$) and the quantity $q = 1$ corresponds to another universe (for which $i^1 = i$) that is invisible for us by virtue of the condition $v > c$, because it is located beyond the event horizon. Stephen William Hawking wrote about imaginary time in such a Multiverse: “*Imaginary time is a new dimension, at right angles to ordinary, real time*”. Thus, his research confirmed the validity of the hypothesis of the hidden Multiverse considered below.

Let us, for definiteness, call the universe corresponding to $q = 1$ a tachyon universe, since it contains tachyons [39]-[40] that are understood to be subatomic particles moving at a speed faster than that of light. Therefore, many physicists believe that they should not exist in nature (by which they mean a Monoverse corresponding to the generally accepted interpretation of the STR), since they violate the principle of causality. However, since tachyons are actually in a tachyon universe (or antiverse), rather than in our universe, they do not violate the principle of causality.

For similar reasons, let us call our universe a tardyon universe. Then it would be logical to assert that the quantity $q = 2$ corresponds to a tardyon antiverse (for which $i^2 = -1$), the quantity $q = 3$ corresponds to a tachyon antiverse (for which $i^3 = -i$), the quantity $q = 4$ corresponds to another tardyon universe (for which $i^4 = 1$), the quantity $q = 5$ corresponds to another tachyon universe (for which $i^5 = i$), etc.

Consequently, such a Multiverse has a helical structure (Fig. 3). Moreover, since $v = w + qc$ follows from the formula $w = v - qc$, then $v > c$ is for all universes, except for ours, and therefore they are beyond the event horizon, i.e. are invisible. The entire Multiverse is also invisible, which is why it is called hidden [41]-[47]. Universes of the hidden Multiverse do not intersect, which is why they can be called parallel. However, drifting in the fourth spatial dimension q they sometimes touch each other and even slightly penetrate into each other, forming some transitional zones called portals [48],[49] (they are shown by double-headed arrows in Fig. 3).

3.2 Dark matter and dark energy phenomena are generated by the existence of the Multiverse

But shown in Fig. 3 structure of the hidden Multiverse has the significant drawback that it does not take into account the existence of the phenomena of dark matter and dark energy, which are not explained. So what are dark matter and dark energy? And why is it so important to explain them? This is because,

according to the data obtained by the WMAP spacecraft, the entire universe (actually, the entire hidden Multiverse) consists of 22.4% of dark matter, 73.0% of dark energy and only 4.6% of baryonic matter [50]. And according to more recent data obtained by the Planck spacecraft, the entire universe (again, actually, the entire hidden Multiverse) consists of 26.8% of dark matter, 68.3% of dark energy and only 4.9% of baryonic substances [51]. That is, according to these data, almost the whole of nature is not at all what we have understood it to be in our visible universe. It is rather different. Thus, without understanding physical sense of dark matter and dark energy, understanding of our visible universe does not seem to be quite reliable. However, despite all the efforts of scientists to solve this important problem, dark matter and dark energy have been defied explanation for almost a hundred years. Michio Kaku wrote in this regard: “*Of course, a whole bunch of Nobel Prizes is waiting for the scientists who can reveal the secrets of the ‘dark energy’ and ‘dark matter’*”.

But all these efforts have actually so far been undertaken within the framework of the generally accepted version of the STR. Therefore, considering the remark of Albert Einstein “*Insanity: doing the same thing over and over again and expecting different results*”, let us now try to seek for such an explanation within the framework of the alternative version of the STR. We should assume what could not be assumed within the framework of the generally accepted version of the STR – to seek for the explanation in the macrocosm, rather than in the microcosm. That is, we should assume that the phenomena of dark matter and dark energy are evoked in our visible universe by the rest of invisible universes of the hidden Multiverse. We should as well assume that the phenomena of dark matter and dark energy [52]-[60] are a kind of optical shadow of these invisible universes on our universe (however, it is gravitational or some other shadow, rather than an electromagnetic one). This will make it possible to understand why, until now, no material carriers of these phenomena have been found by research at the Large Hadron Collider. After all, no optical image (including a shadow) has ever contained any physical components of such an image.

Then, having made such an assumption, it might be argued that:

- the phenomenon of dark matter is evoked by invisible universes of the hidden Multiverse adjacent to our visible universe, and
- the phenomenon of dark energy is evoked by the rest of invisible universes of the hidden Multiverse, more distant from our visible universe.

Herewith, since these universes do not intersect anywhere, they are parallel. However, floating in space, they inevitably touch and even slightly penetrate into each other in many spots, generating portals. Adjacent universes exchange their material content through these portals. Therefore, over billions of years of their existence, parameters of all universes have substantially averaged. And this allows you to

determine the number of universes in the hidden Multiverse. Assuming that our visible universe has such averaged parameters, we can find the following:

- the total number of universes in the hidden Multiverse is $100\% / 4.6\% = 21.74$ according to the above data obtained by the WMAP spacecraft, and $100\% / 4.9\% = 20.41$ according to the data obtained by the Planck spacecraft. Consequently, their real number is supposedly equal to 20...22 universes.

- the number of universes in the hidden Multiverse that are adjacent to our universe and evoke the phenomenon of dark matter is $22.4\% / 4.6\% = 4.87$ according to the above data obtained by the WMAP spacecraft, and $26.8\% / 4.9\% = 5.47$ according to the data obtained by the Planck spacecraft. Consequently, their real number is supposedly equal to 5...6 universes.

- the number of universes in the hidden Multiverse that evoke the phenomenon of dark energy is $73.0\% / 4.6\% = 15.87$ according to the above data obtained by the WMAP spacecraft, and $68.3\% / 4.9\% = 13.94$ according to the data obtained by the Planck spacecraft. Consequently, their real number is supposedly equal to 14...16 universes.

3.3 Dark matter and dark energy phenomena allow to determine the structure of the hidden Multiverse

And immediately striking is the discrepancy between the obtained calculation results and the one shown above in Fig. 3 supposed structures of the hidden Multiverse, which cannot be explained in any way by the inaccuracy of the measurements of the WMAP and Planck spacecraft, since the difference between the

results of calculations and experimental data is too large. There has been found to be five or six other parallel universes adjacent to our universe, rather than two. However, this number does not fit within the structure shown in Fig. 3.

Hence, it is logical to assume that there has been some mistake in the previous reasoning. This mistake, most likely, is that earlier, for simplicity, we have supposed the existence of only one extra dimension q in the hidden Multiverse, and, therefore, its correspondence to physically real complex numbers containing only one imaginary unit. In order for six other parallel universes to be adjacent to our universe (i.e. three tachyon universes and three tachyon antiverses), there should be three extra dimensions q, r, s , determining their position in space. Therefore, the structure of the hidden Multiverse should be described by quaternions $\sigma + i_1\omega_1 + i_2\omega_2 + i_3\omega_3$, i.e. hypercomplex numbers [61], containing three imaginary units i_1, i_2, i_3 connected by

the relations

$$i_1^2 = i_2^2 = i_3^2 = -1 \tag{10}$$

$$i_1i_2i_3 = i_2i_3i_1 = i_3i_1i_2 = -1 \tag{11}$$

$$i_1i_3i_2 = i_2i_1i_3 = i_3i_2i_1 = 1 \tag{12}$$

That is why, the relativistic formulas (4)-(6) and (7)-(9) must be corrected again as follows

$$m(q, r, s) = \frac{m_0 i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s}{\sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2}} \tag{13}$$

Fig. 4. Probable structure of the hidden Multiverse corresponding to the data obtained by the WMAP and Planck spacecraft

Fig. 5. Another probable structure of the hidden Multiverse corresponding to the data obtained by the WMAP and Planck spacecraft

$$\Delta t(q, r, s) = \Delta t_0 i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s \sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2} \tag{14}$$

$$l(q, r, s) = l_0 i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s \sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2} \tag{15}$$

or

$$m(q, r, s) = \frac{m_0 e^{iq\pi/2} e^{ir\pi/2} e^{is\pi/2}}{\sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2}} \tag{16}$$

$$\Delta t(q) = \Delta t_0 e^{iq\pi/2} e^{ir\pi/2} e^{is\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2} \tag{17}$$

Fig. 6. One more probable structure of the hidden Multiverse corresponding to the data obtained by the WMAP and Planck spacecraft

$$l(q) = l_0 e^{iq\pi/2} e^{ir\pi/2} e^{is\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q+r+s)]^2} \tag{18}$$

where m is the relativistic mass of a moving body;

Δt is the relativistic time of a moving body;

l is the relativistic length of a moving body;

q, r, s are the coordinates of the universe in which a moving body is located.

These formulas implies that our Multiverse has a quaternion structure in six-dimensional space [62]-[64] and its structure is described by the function

$f_{q,r,s}(x, y, z) + i_1q + i_2r + i_3s$, where the real summand $f_{q,r,s}(x, y, z)$ describes distribution of physical content in the universe with coordinates q, r, s , and the imaginary summand $i_1q + i_2r + i_3s$ describes the position of this universe in the space of the Multiverse.

According to the formulas (4)-(6), for integers³ of the coordinates of the universes q, r, s in the hidden Multiverse

- we get $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = 1$ for $q + r + s = 0$, which corresponds to our visible universe, which we shall call it a tardyon universe, since we have $0 \leq v < c$ in this case;
- we get either $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = i_1$ or $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = i_2$ or $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = i_3$ for $q + r + s = 1$, which corresponds to one of the invisible universes adjacent to our universe; we shall call them tachyon universes, since we have $v > c$ in this case;
- we get $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = -1$ for $q + r + s = 2$, which corresponds to an invisible tardyon antiverse that is not adjacent to our universe;
- we get either $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = -i_1$ or $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = -i_2$ or $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = -i_3$ for $q + r + s = 3$, which corresponds to one of the invisible tachyon antiverses that is not adjacent to our universe;
- we get $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = 1$ for $q + r + s = 4$, which corresponds to another tardyon, but invisible, universe;
- etc.

Examples of the structural diagrams of the hidden Multiverses corresponding to the calculations are shown in fig. 4-6. As can be seen, the universes contained in these Multiverses are interconnected not only by bidirectional portals corresponding to the formula

(10), but also by unidirectional portals corresponding to the formulas (11) and (12). Besides, some universes of the hidden Multiverse, including our visible universe, it appears, can be connected through portals with universes of other Multiverses that together form a Hyperuniverse⁴, generating the phenomenon of dark space [65], [66].

4. How to see invisible universes

So, the alternative version of the STR successfully solves the problems that turned out to be unsolvable for the generally accepted version. Nevertheless, it will remain but a hypothesis until it finds experimental confirmation. What experimental confirmations of its truth will be authoritatively convincing and how can they be obtained?

Experimental confirmations of real physical existence of the hitherto undetected invisible universes would obviously be the most authoritative evidence. It turns out that one can see [67]-[71], or, in other words, discover them. This requires placing a telescope in a portal⁵ and comparing its observations of the starry sky with the observations of telescopes located outside the portals (Fig. 7). Constellations in the skies of other universes would actually be completely different. Therefore, once a hypothetical telescope is moved through a portal from our universe (i.e. from the earth's surface) to an adjacent universe invisible on Earth, all the known constellations in the starry sky would gradually be replaced by the constellations of the adjacent universe. This would be the most obvious and indisputable evidence of existence of other universes. And such an experiment will be much less expensive than a similar experiment a hundred years ago by the President of the Royal Astronomical Society, Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington [72], [73].

Fig. 7. Diagram of an astronomical experiment on invisible universe detection

³ And non-integer values q, r, s are taken in portals

⁴ By analogy with the term 'Multiverse', hereinafter, instead of 'Hyperuniverse', we will use the term 'Hyperverse'.

⁵ Similarly, to see the invisible neighbouring room of our dwelling, you need to look into it from the corridor connecting these rooms

Fig. 8. The Main Astronomical Observatory of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine located in an anomalous zone

Moreover, some observatories, such as, for example, the Main Astronomical Observatory of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (Fig. 8) located in the Holosiivskyi forest, just 12 km from the centre of Kyiv, the capital of Ukraine, are already in anomalous zones, presumably being entrances to portals. Other observatories also located in anomalous zones can be identified by similar comparative studies of high-precision astronomical observations of all observatories. It is also desirable to subject all anomalous zones to such an examination so that to determine passport data of all portals available on Earth. Their comparative analysis will reveal how many adjacent invisible universes there are on the Earth and determine whether there are universes among these invisible universes that are not the part of the hidden Multiverse. Exploration of such universes would be the most interesting, as it makes possible to discover the Hyperverses.

In the future, when the portals are explored and people learn how to navigate through them safely, people can visit adjacent universes that are currently invisible. This would be another proof of their existence.

5. The relevance of geophysical researches of portals

At present, portals are absolutely unexplored. This even raises doubts as to their existence. Herewith, although there are a lot of anomalous zones supposedly being the entrances to portals, people avoid visiting them. And they are right. This is unsafe, because portals are a kind of invisible labyrinths, three-dimensional labyrinths. So, naturally, finding a way out of a portal is not easy without knowing this and taking special precautions in advance (for example, the Ariadne's thread mentioned in ancient Greek mythology). Even more difficult is to successfully move from entrance to exit through a portal (the Ariadne's thread would not help here) and get into an adjacent universe. To do this, you need to create special tools for orientation in the portals.

But all the means used for a serious portal research, including portal orientation tools, vehicles

(including unmanned vehicles), communications equipment and everything else, are much less expensive than people's flights to the Moon or Mars and much more effective in terms of quantity and quality of new expected knowledge, both astrophysical and geophysical. From the standpoint of scientific, as well as political and economic consequences for human civilization development this would appear to be much more crucial than, for example, the discovery of America by Columbus.

6. Conclusion

Thus, because the fallacy of the universally recognized version of STR stated in physics textbooks, which asserts the existence in nature of our only visible universe, is experimentally proven in the most indisputable way, and the alternative version of this theory states that there are many parallel universes, it has also been proven that there are portals between these universes.

And these portals need to be explored. This is very important from a practical point of view, since one must know how one can safely visit neighboring universes. This is no less important from a scientific point of view, as it will prove the existence of anti-space and anti-time and the possibility of traveling through the hidden Multiverse not only in space, but also in time. Moreover, time travel can be not only in the past, but also in the future [74]-[78].

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